

Scientific article

Design-friendly wind farm control setpoint estimation via layout-agnostic graph neural networks

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Published on: Journal of Physics: Conference Series, Volume 3224, Proceedings of TORQUE 2026, Bruges (3–5 June 2026)

Abstract: *Wind farm control improves energy production, but determining optimal control setpoints is computationally demanding, especially under uncertainty. Wind farm design, operational optimizations, and hybrid design involve many evaluations of optimal setpoints when design and control variables are coupled, a problem known as control co-design. In this work, we first establish a wake steering optimization reference by solving yaw setpoints, taking into account uncertainties in global wind speed, direction, and yaw. We then introduce a Graph Neural Network (GNN) surrogate model for computationally efficient estimation of the control setpoints under uncertainty with wind farm geometry and ambient inflow as the inputs. The proposed GNN is benchmarked against prior computationally efficient and design-friendly methods. The prior models and the GNN are shown to provide wake steering benefits across a wide variety of layout and inflow cases under uncertainty. Across a wide range of wind farm layouts and inflow cases evaluated under uncertainty, the GNN model introduced in this study delivers 98% of the wake steering benefits compared to direct optimization. Beyond the control setpoints, the GNN surrogate model provides accurate multivariate predictions, including power, rotor effective wind speed, and turbulence intensity in a single forward pass, offering additional capabilities for surrogate-based control co-design under uncertainty.*

Link to article: <https://iopscience.iop.org/volume/1742-6596/3224>

SUDOCO is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101122256). Views and opinions expressed herein are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.